

The Similarities and Differences of Structural Types of Antonyms in English and Uzbek Languages

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Annotation: The article aims to reveal the lexical-semantic nature of antonyms in the Uzbek language, considers its types in terms of their structure, their lexical meaning. Also, the typology of the Uzbek and English antonyms is discussed and explained with examples.

Key words: Prefix, affix, suffix, derivative, and compound antonyms, single-root and multi-root antonyms, proper-complex, paired and compound antonyms.

Antonymy could be a widespread phenomenon observed totally different languages and at diverse levels of the language framework. It plays an vital part in speech-thinking movement, since it is the most expressive means of making differentiate. The equivocal and multidimensional approach to the definition of antonymy, to the comes about of investigate in this range, as well as the materials of lexicographic handling displayed within the word references of antonyms, permit us to state that antonymy could be a rather conflicting phenomenon. One of the strategies of profound entrance into the essence of a phonetic wonder is its comparative-typological investigation, revealing the all inclusive and particular in each of the compared dialects in connection to a particular etymological unit and category.

We must look into the essence of antonyms in order to expose their nature. However, there is disagreement even on this matter, particularly when it comes to determining what exactly makes up antonyms, which are actual opposites that exist only in the "meaning of words" or something different. The goal of antonym comparative analysis is to find typological parallels and dissimilarities between languages. Antonyms are one of the linguistic phenomena that has not received enough attention Uzbek linguistics. The goal of researching antonyms in variously structured languages is to create standards for the structural categorization of antonyms, research classification principles, and examine words that comprise antonymic pairs based on derivational models. We must look into the essence of antonyms in order to expose their nature. However, there is disagreement even on this matter, particularly when it comes to determining what exactly makes up antonyms, which are actual opposites that exist only in the "meaning of words" or

something different. The aim of antonym contrastive analysis is to find typological parallels and dissimilarities between languages. Antonyms are one of the linguistic phenomena that has not received enough attention Uzbek linguistics. The goal of researching antonyms in variously structured languages is to create standards for the structural categorization of antonyms, research classification principles, and examine words that comprise antonymic pairs based on derivational models.

Antonyms vary in terms of their structure. Some linguists only include words with opposing sounds that sound different in antonyms, such as "good-yaxshi" and "bad-yomon," "pure-toza" and "dirty-iflos," "joy-quvonch" and "sadness-qayg'u." Other scientists pair up words with positive evaluations and words with negative evaluations; negation is expressed with the negative prefixes -un, -less; for example, compare comfy and uncomfortable or interesting and uninteresting, or use the prefix i: to make something tasty and tasteless or useful and useless[1].

They correspond to the antonymic pairs of Uzbek language with the suffixes -li and -siz and prefix -be: aqlli- aqlsiz, odobli-odobsiz. Different languages have different systems for classifying antonyms. This seems to result from either the selected principles and criteria or the characteristics of the studied language's structural type. The English language has three categories of antonyms: simple, derivative, and compound. Simple antonyms are those that don't contain any suffixes or prefixes: to give 'bermoq' instead of taking 'olmoq,' white 'oq' instead of black 'qora,' day 'kun' instead of night 'tun,' cold' sovuq '-hot' issiq '.Derivative antonyms include words that contain prefixes or suffixes, or both prefixes and suffixes: happy 'baxtli' - unhappy 'baxtsiz', attractive 'jozibali' - unattractive 'jozibasiz, xunuk', equality' tenglik '- inequality' tengsizlik ', correct 'to'g'ri'- incorrect 'noto'g'ri' '. Compound antonyms are formed from two words: to switch on 'yoqmoq' – to switch off o'chirmoq, lowland 'pastlik' - highland 'balandlik', broad-minded 'dunyo qarashi keng' –narrow minded 'dunyo qarashi tor', northland 'shimoliy mamlakatlar' - southland 'janubiy mamlakatlar'. Prefixes, suffixes, or both can be found in derivative antonyms: joyful 'baxtli' - unhappy 'baxtsiz', lovely 'jozibali' - unattractive 'jozibasiz, xunuk', equality tenglik '- inequality' tengsizlik ', correct 'to'g'ri' - incorrect 'noto'g'ri' '. The following are examples of compound antonyms: broad-minded 'dunyo qarashi keng' - narrow-minded 'dunyo qarashi tor', lowland 'pastlik' - highland 'balandlik', northland' shimoliy mamlakatlar' - southland 'janubiy mamlakatlar'.

M.I. Fomina and L.A. Novikov divide the antonyms based on the structural principle into two categories: 1) multiroot, where the opposite is expressed in different words: early - late, life - death, north - south, and single-root antonyms, the antonyms of

which are transmitted either by means of mutually opposite prefixes attached to the same word, or by adding a prefix that gives the original word the opposite meaning: bring in... Sentence construction was recalled for such synonyms [1: 141, 3:21].

Under antonymy, it is necessary to consider not only the opposition of some words of different roots, but also the features of single-root antonyms in their relation to lexical antonyms. R. Shukurov, considering the single-root words of the Uzbek language, formed with the help of the affixes - li, - siz, - ba, - be, - bar, - but, - hush, - bad, etc., recognizes them as antonyms. He recognizes single-rooted pairs as antonymous, since the components express a new lexical meaning, and this can be confirmed by the selection of equivalents in another language, while the equivalents must also be in antonymic relations, for example, baxtli - baxtsiz have antonymous single-root equivalents in Russian: счастливый - несчастливый, in German: glücklich – unglücklich [4: 168]. The antonyms of the Turkmen language were studied by B. Baizhanov [2: 170].

The structural classification of the antonyms of the Uzbek language differs significantly from the classification of the antonyms of the Russian and English languages: as in Uzbek language the main emphasis is on word production of antonymic pairs (root or derivative word), and in the English languages it is highlighted whether the antonyms are single root words or only words, consisting of different roots. In Uzbek language, the phenomenon of enantiosemia is hardly observed: the Yondi 'light bulb burned out' - Yondi 'light bulb has lit up'. In fact, logically, enantiosemia leads to antonymic pairs. However, enantiosemic antonyms were not included in the structural classification of antonyms. When structurally classifying the antonyms of Uzbek language, one should pay attention to the euphemistic antonyms: chiroyli- xunuk and chiroyli–chiroyli emas 'beautiful - ugly'. When studying antonymic pairs, one must take into account their relationship with words, phrases, phraseological units, with polysemy, with synonymy, etc., and all these aspects can be reflected only in a complete dictionary of antonyms. For example, if the Germanic languages and the Russian language have such dictionaries that meet all the requirements, then in the Uzbek language it is necessary to develop new principles and structure for the presentation of antonymic pairs.

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